

Management through the CSR Approach, A Factor of Sustainable Development: Plea for an Imperative Practice in Drc's Companies

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Abstract:- The mode of production of goods and services practiced by companies is the basis for the disruption of planetary balances.

This is how the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) approach is worth its weight in gold. It turns out to be the solution to the Greenhouse Gas (GHG) problem caused by businesses.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a proactive approach to which the company is committed to resolve the problem of global warming.

However, what is voluntary does not have a binding character, so environmental degradation risks increasing without there being any obligation to repair it at the appropriate time.

This is why it is time for the CSR approach to no longer be voluntary but rather a

Obligation for all companies established in the DRC, which is the second lung in the world which provides the environmental solution.

The DRC, thanks to its vegetation, provides the solution to the environmental problem at the global level and, alongside this vegetation, it would be better for companies producing greenhouse gases, which causes global warming, to practice in a manner the CSR approach is mandatory so that Sustainable Development is ensured by companies, an approach which allows a significant reduction in atmospheric pollution.

This requires the cooperation of all stakeholders in the company for its effectiveness.

Keywords:- CSR – Sustainable Development – Stakeholders – Business – Voluntarist – Mode of production – Mandatory – GHG – Pollution – Environment – Global warming.

I. INTRODUCTION

The United Nations Organization (UN), in its role as arbiter in the world continues to multiply calls, to sound the alarm to make it understood, on the one hand, the danger that humanity is in the process of run towards one's environment based on one's behavior and on the other hand, the different models of behavior that one should adopt in order not to reach irreparable environmental damage.

Multiple research and analyzes have demonstrated that it is human beings who are at the root of the disruption of environmental balances in their way of producing goods and services (businesses) and the average person, in their way of consuming.

Since the birth of the industrial era in the 19th century, until today, the environment has only suffered acts of destruction from man who does anything to satisfy his needs and desires. without taking into account environmental balances (meteorological and ecosystems).

It has been revealed that companies, in their way of manufacturing goods and/or providing services, emit more and more greenhouse gases (GHG) which destroy over time, the ozone layer, which causes that planet Earth continues to record an increase in temperature.

We continue to record pollution of the sea, rivers, soil, etc., nuclear disasters, the melting of polar ice, the exhaustion of natural resources, the rise in ocean waters, the increase in quantities of waste. non-recyclable in waterways, climate change, etc.

All these misdeeds continue to disrupt the pre-established environmental balances in a natural way and when these are disrupted, we directly see that Sustainable Development is threatened, or even jeopardized, if we are not careful.

Sustainable Development could be understood as a set of precautions in the way we act today towards the environment in order to allow it to evolve in the direction of respecting natural balances with a view to ensuring a harmonious future.

It is therefore a process that must involve everyone in order to succeed; there should not be actors on the one hand and observers on the other.

The various reports from the Conference of the Parties (COP) indicate that there are certain countries that are still lagging behind in the application of the various recommendations resulting from different meetings.

The current state of planet Earth requires the rapid and flawless application of the various COP recommendations, with a view to quickly achieving the expected results.

- The result is that a rapid and unwavering awareness must lead to the application of the various recommendations before it is late, because the repair will be expensive, to the extent that certain balances already affected require a lot of time and a lot of efforts, for example, according to

the experts of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, IPCC in acronym, it takes approximately a thousand years for a centimeter of soil is not replenished, which means that we will not be able to produce any balance during our lifetime (in the case of soil pollution).

The constitution of the Democratic Republic of Congo, in its article 53, stipulates: “every person has the right to a healthy environment conducive to their full development. She has a duty to defend him. The State ensures the protection of the environment and the health of populations¹

This article takes this constitutional provision as a plea for mandatory application. Indeed, the imperative aspect is mentioned there but in reality, the CSR approach is **proactive** in the head of the company, which is a major player in the current state of planet Earth, characterized by disruptions in the natural balance, due much more to GHG emissions.

Thus, it is made up of the following points:

- History of CSR;
- Current state of planet Earth;
- The environmental limits of planet Earth;
- CSR and Sustainable Development;
- Economy and Biodiversity;
- Conclusion.

II. HISTORY OF CSR

A. Advent of CSR.

The concept of “Corporate Social Responsibility” dates from the 1950s and appeared for the first time through the work of Howard BOWER, more precisely in 1953. Still in this context, appeared in 1961, the work of G. GOYDER, entitled: “The Responsible corporation”.

Some authors have divided the advent of CSR into three trends or periods, namely:

- The first current called “business ethics”, it goes from 1950 – 1960. During this period, CSR focuses on the personal moral responsibility of the company manager;
- The second movement called “utilitarian strategic” was during the 1970s, here CSR is embodied in the idea that responsible behavior improves the economic performance of companies;
- The third current, described as “emerging current”, has taken place since the Rio summit in Brazil in 1992, the main idea is, the company must contribute to Sustainable Development.

The current state of planet Earth, from an ecological point of view, has for more than a decade led people to say that there is an emergency and that something must be done to save the situation of the planet, characterized by global warming, nuclear disasters, pollution of air, soil, water, etc.

All these environmental phenomena could trigger a reaction in “conscious humans” which pushes them to take actions that will allow the situation to be repaired.

In this wake of awareness and the search for a solution, the CSR approach will appear. The current state of planet Earth makes man designated as being at the center of this situation, or rather the sole responsible for the situation, given his mode of production and consumption.

Given that the company is a legal entity, producing goods and services that it makes available to the market, is concerned, or even indexed, will have to change its way of acting.

The French Ministry of Ecological and Social Transition defines CSR as “a concept in which companies integrate social, environmental and economic concerns into their activities and in their interactions with their stakeholders on a voluntary basis”². in fact the obligation that the company gives itself, in addition to the obligations imposed on it by the law and the economic system, to pursue long-term objectives serving the bond of the entire community

We will realize that CSR is an awareness of the danger that is looming on the horizon. In our opinion, this approach should be practiced imperatively in all companies in the DRC.

Like any human reality, there are antagonistic opinions regarding the CSR approach, some for and others against.

B. ANTAGONISM AROUND CSR

According to Milton Friedman, only human beings have moral responsibility for their actions. Company managers only have responsibility towards the shareholders of the company, as for environmental responsibility, it falls to the State. The first social responsibility in the coming decade is to create capital, which alone can finance the jobs of tomorrow. The sole responsibility of the company is to use its resources in activities designed to increase its profits as long as it remains within the rules of the game. Also, taking into account CSR implies additional financial costs consequently causing a competitive disadvantage.

Friedman will be contradicted by authors like R. Edward Freeman, Cattel -Horn Carroll, notably³:

For R.E Freeman, the objective of a business is not to amass profit. The problem is this, the company focuses on shareholders and forgets the other people impacted by the company's activity. According to his theory, the purpose of a business is to meet the needs of the stakeholders that make up society. Businesses have a real impact on our societies through their positive but also negative externalities.

¹Constitution of the Democratic Republic of CONGO, promulgated on February 18, 2006, art. 53

²www.ecologie.gouv.fr, accessed January 7, 2022

³www.escadrille.org, accessed January 10, 2022

They have real decision-making power; as powerful social actors, companies have many substantial resources. It is within their power to use them responsibly within society; since society and business are mutually interdependent.

Cattel -Horn, defines CSR as: "The attempt by businesses to meet the economic, legal, ethical and philanthropic requirements of a given society at a given time".

For this purpose, it identifies 4 responsibilities at the company level through a pyramid:

- Legal responsibilities (legal responsibilities): society demands that businesses follow the law;
- Economic responsibilities (economic responsibilities): society demands that businesses follow the law;
- Ethical responsibilities (ethical responsibilities): society expects businesses to behave ethically;
- Philanthropic responsibilities (philanthropic responsibilities): society wants businesses to do good for the community.

From these two camps of discussions, we can say that:

Milton Friedman's thesis is found in a certain context given at the time, but today it is outdated. At the time when this thesis was put forward, certainly the effects of global warming and others were not as acutely posed as they are today.

Starting from the notion of stakeholders, Mr. Friedman's thesis is limiting (probably because it is prior to this one), it only refers to one (shareholders), whereas the notion of stakeholders is globalizing and indivisible.

On the other hand, the theses of RE Freeman and Cattel are evolving and fit with what is required as an attitude that the company must adopt given the characteristics presented by the environment.

The abuses that man causes towards the environment are increasingly permissive; if we do not change our modes of production and consumption, planet Earth risks being unlivable.

Planet Earth today presents a bleak picture, which is what we will address in the following point.

III. CURRENT STATE OF PLANET EARTH

The sociologist Emile Durkheim said: "Such type of technology, such type of society ⁴".

Society, better still, planet Earth, today is characterized by increasingly advanced technological advancement which brings innovation to innovation.

This is what climatologists Will Steffen, Paul Cruzen and historian John Mc Neill described as the "Great Acceleration" due to human activity which, in recent years, has profoundly altered ecosystems, compared to other historical periods. This is why environmental concerns have emerged ⁵.

Man's modes of production and consumption have led to the environment of planet Earth experiencing the following problems: water pollution, soil pollution, air pollution, exhaustion resources, the massive disappearance of plant and animal species, the depletion of biodiversity, global warming, etc. Let's now look at each of these problems in a little detail.

A. Global warming

Global warming, also called global warming, is a global phenomenon of climate transformation characterized by a general increase in average temperatures (in particular linked to human activities), and which lastingly modifies weather balances and ecosystems ⁶.

Analyzes have shown that it is human activities which are the basis of this increase in average temperature which is between 1 to 1.5°C above average temperature. This increase in temperature is nothing other than the consequence of the emission of greenhouse gases (GHG).

A certain scientist, by the name of Svante Arrhenius, who for the first time, in 1890, discovered that when the air is charged with carbon dioxide, it retains more heat from solar radiation which in turn causes an increase in temperature air.

The fact that the air is loaded with carbon dioxide, which retains more heat from solar radiation, we speak of polluted air. According to scientists, the share of carbon dioxide in global warming is 63%.

⁴LOMBEYA B., General Sociology Course, G1, Faseg, UNIKIN, 1990, Unpublished

⁵www.fr.Wikipedia.org, consulted on February 9, 2022

⁶www.youmatter, accessed February 7, 2022

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, IPCC in acronym, the United Nations' consultative body par excellence on global warming, published its latest report on this subject, on April 7, 2022 at 5:00 p.m. report is summarized in the following 5 recommendations ⁷:

A. Ending fossil fuels

Companies must abandon coal mining by 2050 and to do this, any subsidies granted in this area must be discouraged, which would reduce GHG emissions by 10% by 2030. Also, we must prohibit the renewal and renovation of coal industries.

B. Turn to renewable energies

For the IPCC, we must be able to abandon coal in favor of solar energy, which moreover is less expensive compared to fossil fuels.

C. Capturing and storing carbon

To achieve the zero CO₂ emissions objective, capture techniques are indicated, although currently, reforestation and trapping methods are used.

D. Change our habits

The IPCC, on this subject, recommends teleworking or carpooling, reducing food waste, increasing the durability of devices, etc.

E. Investing for a better world

For the IPCC, it is necessary to significantly increase investments in the environmental sector in order to avoid exceeding the symbolic bar of 2° C. The level of these investments, for the IPCC, should be between 3 to 6 times the level 2020 investments.

B. Water pollution

Water is a healer of the souls of humanities (Bantou Proverb).

Water pollution occurs when there are micro-organisms, chemical substances and industrial waste in the water, that is to say, an excess of harmful materials. This pollution can be chemical, bacteriological or thermal .

Tables of water, rivers, brackish water, rainwater, polar ice, dew and snow are susceptible to pollution.

Water pollution causes water-borne diseases (diarrhea, etc.) but also effects that are described as “less visible”, such as eutrophication of environments. Eutrophication refers to a process of accumulation of nutrients in a given ecosystem. It leads to a deficit in biodiversity; ultimately, in an aquatic environment, it can cause chronic anoxia (oxygen deprivation) which proves fatal for most species ⁸. There are also toxic effects, endocrine disruption

When there is water pollution, the surrounding population suffers harmful consequences from the situation, including:

- The case of the pollution of the Kasai and Tshikapa rivers, which took place in August 2021, causing the death of 12 people, two hippos in Ilebo, the loss of aquatic flora, water-borne diseases for local populations; there was also disruption of fishing and navigation activities, lack of access to water for domestic use and recreation. The table below summarizes the situation of this disaster:

⁷www.journaldugeek.com, consulted on April 9, 2022

⁸www.youmatter.world, accessed March 13, 2022

Table 1: Summary of the pollution situation of the KASAI and TSHIKAPA rivers

Number of complaints	Victims	Charged facts	Consequences	Incriminated	Observation
7879	Riverine populations (Kasaï and Tshikapa)	Pollution of two rivers: Kasaï and Tshikapa	Death of men, animals, diseases	CATOCA DIAMOND company, established in Angola	\$100 billion in terms of repairs

Source: Author

As we can see, the number of complaints is high, which means the damage is also high. Furthermore, as the case is before the judicial authorities, its outcome involves diplomatic channels and private international law.

The RUZIZI hydroelectric plant, during the month of March, experienced stoppages in electricity supplies for weeks, due to the pollution of its waters which are invaded by significant layers of plastic bottles.

Such a situation can only cause a loss of income for local businesses and households, but also hospitals where such a situation risks causing a cascade of deaths, but also the rapid decomposition of the bodies found in the various morgues, if there are no practical arrangements for this.

On the other hand, at the end of the 9th world water forum held very recently, from March 21-26, 2022, in

Dakar, Senegal, which had the sub-theme “water security for peace and development”, the UN announces:

- More than 2 billion people in the world lack water;
- Only 30% of the world's population has a safe source of water.
- 500 million inhabitants spread across 19 African countries do not have assured access to water
- As for the European Union and 13 other countries, organized in Brest (in France), from February 9 – 12, 2022, a summit which calls for the adoption this year of an ambitious treaty for marine biodiversity in the area - beyond national jurisdictions; because they judge, the oceans are poorly known and poorly protected.
- Plastic waste constitutes a serious pollution problem, it is counted among the biggest pollutants on the planet. The production of plastic bottles is only increasing from year to year.

Table 2: Evolution of production of plastic bottles in the world (in tonnes)

1993	2015	2022 (until the 1 st quarter)
162,000,000	448,000,000	6,900,000,000

Source: Author, based on available data

It appears that between 1993 and 2015, the increase is 176.54% and per year the average increase is 5.89%. Furthermore, between 2015 and the first quarter of the

current year, the increase is 1,530.18% and the annual average is 191.27%.

Table 3: Treatments reserved for plastic waste (in percentage)

Recycled	Cremented	Accumulated in landfills (including watercourses)
9%	12%	79%

Source: Author, based on available data

It appears that the majority of plastic waste is lying around either in landfills or in nature (waterways and on the ground here and there). The portion treated and/or incinerated only represents a third of what is present. is not processed.

It was reported in March (mid-March) of the current year that there was melting of ice in Antarctica, with an area of 12,000 km², as a result of global warming⁹.

When ice melts, this leads to an increase in water levels which could lead to flooding of towns, cities, etc., in short the world becomes unlivable.

C. Soil pollution

Soil is said to be polluted when it contains an abnormal concentration of chemical compounds potentially dangerous to the health of plants or animals¹⁰.

For the Virtual Dictionary, Wikipedia, the notion of soil pollution designates all forms of pollution affecting any type of soil, particularly agricultural, forestry, urban, etc.

Soil pollution impacts plant metabolism, which leads to a reduction in agricultural yield, resulting in food insecurity.

In this regard, we will remember the accusations launched against the “ Perenco company ” by the Senate in 2012, for having polluted the water, air and land in Muanda , in the Kongo province.

– central, and according to the group of Congolese and Angolan fishermen (among the victims), this pollution had caused the disappearance of different species of fish.

Perenco company ” was the subject of another complaint brought against it by two NGOs, namely Sherpa and Friends of the Earth. The complaint was filed with the Paris Court, where the two NGOs held the same grievances

⁹www.ouest-france.fr, consulted on March 22, 2022

¹⁰www.risksenvironnementals-collectivites.oree.org, consulted on March 24, 2022

against the Perenco company. Unfortunately, both organizations were unsuccessful.

The Strategic Institute for Sustainable Development announces the decline in vegetable production due to global warming¹¹.

The Congo Basin forest, the 2nd largest forest in the world after the Amazon (Brazil) and the world's lung, poses a problem for its management, basically a lack of transparency in the allocation of operating permits¹².

In Lubumbashi, the Chinese company Congo Dongfang Mining is accused of dumping huge quantities of wastewater in the Kasapa, Kamatete and Kamisepe districts, causing flooding and erosion, thus polluting the water and the soil.

The NGO Afrewatch wanted to know more, so investigated the situation and based on the samples taken, it was concluded that there was indeed soil and soil pollution.

In Brazil, in the Amazon, which is the first lung of the planet, we deplore exaggerated deforestation of up to 430 km² in January 2022; which is 5 times as in January 2021.

¹¹Radio Okapi, spoken news 8:00 a.m. edition, March 31, 2022

¹²RFI, spoken news 8:30 a.m. edition, March 30, 2022

Table 4: Evolution of deforestation (in km²) of the Amazon

Periods	January 2021	January 2022	Change (%)
Deforested area	86	430	400

Source: Author, based on available information.

The table indicates that in the space of 12 months, therefore 1 year, the deforested area is 400%, so the monthly average is 33.33%, which is enormous.

D. Air pollution

Air pollution is an alteration in the quantity of air that can be characterized by measurements of chemical, biological or physical pollutants. It can have harmful consequences for human health, living beings, the climate or materials (Wikipedia).

Air pollution leads to several types of diseases, including asthma, conjunctivitis, allergy, lung cancer, cardiovascular diseases, etc.

Air pollution is the result of industrial activity in the exploitation of coal, oil and gas, mainly. The air that emerges from this exploitation is loaded with greenhouse gases, that is to say, carbon dioxide, in large part, but also methane, retains more solar radiation and this is what leads an increase in air temperature.

Following its mining activity, the Tenke company Fungurume Mining, TFM in acronym, was taken to court by the Soleil party which accused it of having polluted the Kabombwa river, of having polluted the environment with dust on the houses of the population, in the province of Lualaba, this in October 2021.

The company Perenco was accused of polluting two territories in Gabon, namely the territory of Oba and Moba¹³.

It should be noted that there is not only pollution coming from human activity, which we qualify as anthropogenic in origin, but there are also natural phenomena, in particular volcanic eruptions, fires. forests; this pollution is of low proportion.

E. Resource depletion

The exponential increase in population across the world pushes the company to increase the supply on the market, and which leads it to wild exploitation, that is to say, uncontrolled exploitation of natural resources with a mode of production which does not take into account respect for environmental balances.

With this uncontrolled exploitation, these natural resources are qualified as "non-renewable", hence we must think about replacing them with other types, but also about reasoned exploitation.

According to some scientists the following natural resources will be exhausted by then¹⁴:

- Coal within 2 to 3 centuries;
- Oil 50 to 100 years;
- Gas 60 to 70 years;
- Slow neutron nuclear power 12 to 60 years, depending on world consumption.

Some people think that to avoid the exhaustion of resources, we must respect the following 4 rules¹⁵:

- Measure your consumption carefully, to avoid depletion of natural resources. Consuming without measuring is like spending without counting;
- Don't waste anything;
- Know how to recycle;
- Raising awareness.

F. The massive disappearance of plant and animal species

The increase in population impacts the level of consumption which increases proportionally to that of the population, resulting in an increase in demand.

Faced with increasing demand, the company is offered an opportunity to maximize its profits, thus it engages in uncontrolled exploitation of the environment.

Likewise, for households, which seek to maximize their utilities (satisfactions), faced with a mentality of non-compliance with environmental standards, they act much more in maximizing their interests to the detriment of environmental standards.

Thus, we are witnessing rampant deforestation, overexploitation of species, and the disappearance of species at an accelerated rate. This rate is estimated to be 1,000 times higher than the so-called natural rate.

G. The depletion of biodiversity

Biodiversity, also called biological diversity, can be defined as the variety of life on earth in all its forms. It includes the number of species, their genetic vegetation and the interaction of these life forms within complex ecosystems¹⁶.

In a UN report published three years ago, some scientists in the field said, 1 million species, out of an estimated 8 million total, are threatened with extinction.

Biological diversity improves the existence of the environment by promoting a good climate, good vegetation, good flora, good soil, clean air, fresh water, but also, it combats global warming.

¹⁴www.ladepeche.fr, consulted on February 13, 2022

¹⁵www.envibio, accessed February 15, 2022

¹⁶www.europarl.europa.eu, accessed February 25, 2022

¹³RFI, spoken news 8:30 a.m. edition, April 2, 2022

Because there is interaction between different forms of life in the ecosystem, the disappearance of a species can have unfortunate consequences on the food chain.

It is said that there are 5 main causes that underlie the loss of biodiversity, namely ¹⁷:

- change in land and sea use (deforestation, urbanization, etc.);
- the direct exploitation of certain organisms (hunting and overfishing);
- climate change ;
- Pollution ;
- invasive exotic species.

Having described the current state of the global environment, let's move on to the next point.

IV. THE ENVIRONMENTAL LIMITS OF PLANET EARTH

The planetary boundaries were established and clarified twice by an international multidisciplinary team. The latter broke down "the earth system" into 9 compartments or parameters or even limits which are:

- Climate ;
- Biodiversity;
- Stratospheric ozone;
- Biochemical cycles;
- Fresh waters;
- Acidity of the ocean;
- Land use;
- Aerosols in the atmosphere;
- New entities.

This team attempted to establish for each of them the level of disturbance below which the risk of destabilization of the Earth system remains low. Conversely, crossing these limits involves the risk of seeing the natural balances which have dominated the planet for several years (11,000 years) irreversibly shift ¹⁸.

To date, 6 of these 9 limits have already been crossed, which is worrying, these are the following limits:

- Biochemical cycles (nitrogen and phosphorus);
- The climate ;
- The erosion of biodiversity;
- Land use;
- Chemical pollution or the introduction and accumulation of new entities in the environment;
- The fresh water cycle.

The last two limits were crossed during this year 2022.

Such a situation should only concern any sensible person and, as a result, they are called upon to change their behavior towards the environment. Let's move on to Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and Sustainable Development (SD).

V. CSR AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

In this point, it is a question of defining the two concepts, namely CSR and Sustainable Development. Next, we will try to identify the link that exists between the two concepts.

A. Definition of CSR

CSR implies that companies integrate social, environmental and economic concerns into their strategies and in their interactions with stakeholders, and on a voluntary basis. It is in fact the obligation that the company gives itself, in addition to the obligations imposed on it by the law and the economic system, to pursue long-term objectives serving the good of the entire community ¹⁹.

For the French Ministry of Ecological Transition, CSR is a concept in which companies integrate social, environmental and economic concerns into their activities and in their interactions with their stakeholders on a voluntary basis ²⁰.

We can say that CSR is a proactive attitude internalizing social, environmental and economic aspects, applied by a company, with the aim of preserving the environment and satisfying all stakeholders.

B. Definition of Sustainable Development

The term "Sustainable Development" was coined in the Brundtland report in 1987. It is defined as development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. This is how it becomes a global challenge ²¹.

The idea of Sustainable Development according to the definition of this report is that it is possible to find an economic model which reconciles the growth of markets and production, with respect for natural limits and human rights ²².

As for us, Sustainable Development is a process which results in a development which guarantees the flourishing of human life in all aspects of it and taking into account the protection of the life of beings today and of the future.

The Brundtland report was written by the United Nations World Commission on Environment and Development, which was chaired by the Norwegian woman, Brundtland.

¹⁷www.biodiversite.gouv.fr , consulted on February 24, 2022

¹⁸FOUCART S., The environment through human activities, In newspaper *Le Monde* , published on January 28, 2022

¹⁹GAMELA 0, Introduction to Corporate Social Responsibility, Kongo University Press, p.26, 2021

²⁰www.ecologie.gouv.fr , consulted on January 7, 2022

²¹www.ecologie.gouv.fr , consulted April 27, 2022

²²www.youmatter.world

VI. LINKS BETWEEN CSR AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

The CSR approach is a Sustainable Development practice at the company level. When the company subscribes to the CSR approach, ipso facto, it materializes Sustainable Development which reconciles environmental protection, economic efficiency and social justice.

It is the same when the company is part of the CSR approach, it reconciles social, economic and environmental aspects with the aim of satisfying all stakeholders.

Furthermore, the company lives in an environment and takes actions that have an impact on the environment and on individuals, and through the CSR approach, it takes into account all its aspects to design its strategies which will make it possible to achieve its assigned objectives which, in principle, take into account the aspirations of everyone.

CSR contributes to Sustainable Development as long as it takes into account the interests of all stakeholders, which is also the objective of Sustainable Development. Likewise, Sustainable Development is a factor in business growth.

There is a compatibility between the CSR approach and Sustainable Development; a company which is part of the CSR approach, thereby practicing the principle of Sustainable Development.

Sustainable Development allows the sustainable company to perpetuate itself, because it brings all stakeholders in agreement on the fact that it takes into account social, environmental, economic aspects and good governance in its strategies, thus, it combines permanently the verbs renew, recycle, conserve and preserve.

It should be noted that a sustainable company is one that subscribes to and pursues Sustainable Development. In other words, it is the one that acts in such a way as to achieve Sustainable Development.

VII. THE ECONOMY AND BIODIVERSITY

It is a question, at this level, of analyzing whether the economic growth recorded by countries around the world, much more highly industrialized countries, will still be effective at the moment when environmental balances, better environmental limits are crossed (six limits on nine have already been crossed) due to global warming.

In light of this issue, points of view diverge in all directions; there are those who think that if nothing is done within the framework of the COP 25 meetings, held in Paris in 2021 and the COP 26 meetings, held in Glasgow in Scotland from November 1 to November 12, 2021, economies will risk to no longer record any growth and planet Earth will become unlivable.

Let us remember that the two main recommendations of these two meetings are:

- Reduce CO₂ emissions, thereby maintaining the rise in temperature at a level of 1.5° C from normal temperature, not exceeding 2° C (COP 25, Paris);
- Reduce methane emissions by around 30% by 2030 (COP 26, Glasgow).

It should be noted that methane is the second most polluting gas, after carbon dioxide (CO₂), moreover, during the Glasgow conference, among the 5 most polluting countries in the world, namely China, India, Iran, Russia and the USA, only the USA which has signed it to date.

In a publication in the French newspaper "Le Monde", appearing in Paris, published on April 9, Dennis Meadows, physicist and co-author of the Club of Rome report "The limits to growth", declares the following: "the imperative is today to change **the values and objectives** of contemporary societies, which are heading towards their ruin.

We did not act. We are therefore beyond Earth's capacity to support us, so the decline of our energy- and material-intensive civilization is inevitable. The standard of living will fall, mortality will increase or the birth rate will be reduced and resources will decrease.

Most people think that resource depletion only affects us when there are none left in the ground. It's more complex than that. The limits to growth are linked to the fact that, gradually, the cost of resources becomes so high that we can no longer afford to use them in such large quantities. We are currently in this situation where, for example, the price of oil is becoming too expensive for consumers²³."

On the other hand, there is a group of researchers from the university college London (United Kingdom), these are reassuring that it is possible for the world's economies to record growth. Their goal was to find out whether the goals of the Paris climate agreement can be achieved in a world of continued economic growth until 2100.

The group states that there will be a slowdown in the growth of global demand for primary energy, then they have modeled the deployment of renewable technologies necessary to decarbonize the production of electricity while producing seven times more than the consumption of 2010.

The IPCC, in its latest report where the group is less pessimistic, published on April 26, speaks of decoupling GDP growth and GHG emissions. It defines "coupling" as the cause and effect relationship between GDP and GHG emissions. In other words, the more growth there is ipso facto, there is GHG emissions. In other words, we cannot record growth without GHGs.

²³MEADOWS D., We must put an end to uncontrolled growth, the cancer of society, In newspaper Le Monde of April 9, 2022

Furthermore, for the IPCC, by seeking to “avoid ecological disasters”, the poorest countries on the planet, therefore the least developed countries, will be incapable of recovering the delay they have recorded compared to the rich and industrial.

On the other hand, the IPCC refers to what it calls “absolute decoupling”, which is nothing other than the decline in the growth of emissions per unit of GDP.

Indeed, according to the IPCC, many countries of the European Union, in total 23 countries, have reduced their carbon footprint of consumption per unit of GDP by around 8% during the period 1995 and 2015, also, among emerging countries, 67 (including China and India) have experienced relative decoupling, which is a positive element for our planet.

By relative decoupling we mean a reduction in ecological intensity per unit of economic production. In this situation, resource impacts decrease relative to GDP, but environmental impact and GDP both increase. (Wikipedia).

On the other hand, households also contribute to global warming in the way they chop down trees, process their waste (especially plastic bottles), exploit the forest, etc.

Thus, it is imperative that everyone, at any level does something within the framework of environmental protection with a view to enabling Sustainable Development.

VIII. CONCLUSION

For a number of years, planet Earth has been experiencing disturbances in its natural balance, which are due to man's mode of production and consumption, which in principle should protect its environment, because its life depends on it; in other words, the way in which man produces and consumes goods and services disrupts the natural balances of planet Earth.

The company, a legal entity, since that is what it is, produces goods and services without respecting the environmental balances that support our planet Earth.

By producing goods and services, the company emits greenhouse gases which pollute the environment, these main gases are: carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), ozone (O₃), protoxide nitrogen (N₂O); by polluting the environment, the consequence is nothing other than global warming which is felt everywhere on planet Earth, making it more and more unlivable.

As such, we are recording phenomena that can be described as "extraterrestrial", which are worrying and threaten human survival, we can cite in particular: the presence of microplastics in human blood²⁴, melting of ice in Antarctica with an area of 12,000 km²²⁵, the loss of sleep

of 44 days on average per year on the part of man, this could reach 50 to 58 days per year by the end of this century²⁶, different diseases, change in size of man in shrinking²⁷, drying up of watercourses; according to NASA, in certain corners of the world, survival will be difficult from 2050: southern Asia, in the Persian Gulf (Iran, Oman, Kuwait), Egypt, Saudi Arabia, Sudan, Ethiopia, Somalia, Yemen²⁸; in May of 2022, a temperature of 50° C was recorded in India, but at 55° C, proteins coagulate, humans also coagulate²⁹.

With all these phenomena in mind, man is called upon to react in order to find the solution to this problem of global warming, and it turns out that the CSR approach happens to be the best way to resolve the problem at the level of the company producing the goods and services.

CSR is nothing other than awareness at the company level to ensure Sustainable Development which is nothing other than respecting the natural environmental balance today to ensure its harmonious future of the environment.

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) declares: “we are heading towards catastrophe if we do nothing, but it is not too late as long as we act quickly”, thus, it formulates a certain number of recommendations to resolve the problem, the main ones are:

A. Ending fossil fuels

- Abandon coal by 2050, while cutting all subsidies granted to polluting energies;

B. Turn to renewable energies

- Use more and more solar energy which, moreover, costs less than fossil energy;

C. Capturing and storing carbon

- Through reforestation and carbon sequestration in the soil;

D. Change our habits

- Reduce food waste and meat consumption. Furthermore, opt for teleworking, carpooling, etc.

E. Investing for a better world

- Increase environmental investments around the world, three to six times more by 2030.
- This article pleads for an imperative application of the CSR approach in the DRC, although it is a voluntary approach. We believe that it must no longer remain proactive, because the current state of the environment requires it, as does the position of our country as a solution country in terms of global warming.

²⁶www.lepoint.fr, consulted on May 21, 2022

²⁷www.futura-sciences.com, accessed May 22, 2022

²⁸www.geo.fr antarctica, accessed on March 22, 2022.

²⁹www.europe1.fr societe ecologie, consulted on June 19, 2022

²⁴www.ouestfrance-emploi.com, consulted on April 19, 2022

²⁵www.ouest-france.fr, consulted on April 21, 2022

In addition, the constitution of the DRC in its article 53 stipulates: “every person has the right to a healthy environment conducive to their full development. She has a duty to defend him. The State ensures the protection of the environment and the health of the population.”

As we can see, it is time for everyone to become aware and act in favor of our planet Earth, so that the irreparable does not happen.

As such, let us share with Michael Porter and Mark Kramer, for them the solution, within the framework of the company, it is therefore necessary to create shared value , which consists of also creating value for society by responding to its needs and challenges, that is to say, reconciling the company's profit objectives with its objectives of social and environmental responsibility, thus, this desire to create shared value must be at the **forefront** . center of companies' wishes to create a link between social progress and economic progress³⁰.

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

A. To the Government

- To revisit all the forestry contracts he has signed, in order to bring order to this sector. To do this, an ad hoc commission is needed made up of delegates from the presidency, the Government, parliament and university experts.
- To allocate the necessary means for the proper functioning of all institutions specializing in environmental matters.
- To establish the practice of periodic accountability and thus, permanently.
- Engage in dialogue with the FEC in favor of the mandatory practice of CSR.
- Introduce environmental courses into primary and secondary education.

B. In Parliament

- To pass a law making the practice of CSR compulsory in all companies established in the DRC.
- Create a subcommittee to monitor the said law in the main environment committee.

C. To the provincial governorates

- To rehabilitate sanitation and hygiene services in cities, capitals, localities, neighborhoods and streets.
- Introduce a transactional fine against any recalcitrant, to make it binding on households.

As we can see, the environmental problem is serious and we must take measures that can help us resolve the various problems linked to the environment, namely: global warming, unsanitary conditions in our living environments, deforestation, pollution of our waterways, etc., in order to ensure Sustainable Development.

To do this, there needs to be **political will**.

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